

A NOTE ON THE CLASSIFICATION OF ELEMENTS

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Since the time of Mendeleeff, the "Periodic Table" has, no doubt, undergone many changes with modifications here and there, but some of its defects still remain to be solved. For example, the position of the rare-earths in the periodic table is a matter of some complexity. Another example is the position of hydrogen. It has not yet been possible to assign any definite position to these elements.

With a view to removing the difficulties, without sacrificing the merits of the existing tables, the following classification based on atomic number and valency electrons is suggested. This mode of representation seems to be simpler and clearer and it is believed, will be more easily intelligible to students. The elements are arranged by plotting their atomic numbers as ordinates and valency electrons as abscissa. By valency electrons is understood, the number of electrons in the highest quantum group of the element together with those in the *d*-level of the preceding group, so long as the latter (*i.e.* *d*-level) is incomplete. The total number of such valency electrons in any element varies from zero to ten but is never greater than ten. When the *d*-level becomes complete, all the valency electrons are supposed to lie in the outermost layer of the element. Thus calcium has two valency electrons, scandium has three, nickel ten, copper one and so on.

Thus, starting with, helium, the elements have been arranged in two short periods, followed by four long periods, the last one being incomplete. Hydrogen is placed along with neutron in series I before the first short period. The elements are also divided according to their valency electrons into eleven vertical groups beginning from 0 to 10 as shown in the table.

The main characteristics which distinguish the present table from the older ones are that (i) the rare-earths having the same number of valency electrons (one in $5-d$ and two in $6-s$) are all placed in group III; (ii) hydrogen having a single valency electron is placed in group I; (iii) the eighth group instead of containing all the nine elements of the three triads contains only one member from each set, the others being placed in groups IX and X. The position of hydrogen in group I explains its similarities not only with the alkali metals but also with the halogens, because, by the gain of an electron, it attains the stable configuration of an inert gas, helium, just as the halogens do.

The inert gases (except He) which have eight electrons in the outermost layer and the full number of electrons in the d -level of the preceding group, should be placed in group VIII, according to the above classification. But considering that these elements have completed the octet and that a new electron if added, would find its way into the next higher quantum group and give rise to an element with one valency electron, the inert gases may also be regarded as having zero number of electrons in the highest and eight electrons in the layer next the highest quantum group. Thus, argon with eight electrons in the M -shell (2 in s , 6 in p , and 0 in d -level) and with no electrons in the N -shell may be said to have zero number of electrons in the highest quantum group. In this way, all the inert gases may be regarded as having no electron either in the highest quantum group or in the d -level of the preceding group. The number of valency electrons of these elements is therefore zero and they are placed in the zero group instead of group VIII.

Another characteristic feature of the present classification is that all the non-transition elements, whose valency electrons lie exclusively in the highest quantum group belong to sub-group A; while the rest, which are all transition elements and whose (except Cu, Ag, Au, Zn, Cd and Hg) valency electrons are distributed into the last two quantum groups belong to sub-group B. Thus every group is divided into two sub-groups A and B; A containing the non-transition elements placed to the left hand side of each vertical line and B containing the rest which are all transition elements, placed to the right as shown in the table*. In the list of transition elements, mentioned above, have been included all the elements (*viz.*, Sc-Zn; Y-Cd; La-Hg and Ac-U) which are formed by the gradual entry of the additional electrons, consequent on increasing atomic number, into the inner layers of the electron shell, instead of the outer layer only being built up.

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